

Enabling a low-carbon electricity system for Southern Africa

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Abstract

Southern Africa faces the dual challenge of providing affordable energy to meet rapidly growing electricity demand while limiting carbon emissions and socio-environmental impacts. To develop optimal electricity pathways for Southern Africa under varying technology and fuel cost projections and energy policies, we combined open source geospatial, hydrologic, and electricity grid-investment models that represent renewable resources in high spatio-temporal detail. We found that if technology and fuel prices continue to

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follow current trends, wind and solar technologies can become the dominant sources of electricity in the region by 2040. Importantly, no new coal capacity was built in any scenario except when inter-regional transmission was constrained. Further, despite the abundant hydropower potential in the region, fewer than half of planned hydropower projects were cost-competitive, thus supporting river conservation efforts. Through continued build-out of renewable energy technologies and coordinated expansion of inter-regional transmission lines and electricity trade, Southern Africa could maintain its GHG emissions in 2040 at 2020 levels. Limiting coal plant lifetimes to 45 years (20 years less compared to reference) could halve emissions, but results in 13% higher total annual system costs. Alternatively, an 80% clean energy target resulted in a similar 50% reduction in annual GHG emissions by 2040 but costs only 6% or USD \$3/MWh more than reference. Our study shows feasible pathways for Southern Africa to develop an affordable and low-carbon electricity system.

Keywords: wind, solar, renewable energy, electricity, Africa

1 **Highlights**

- 2 • We develop optimal 2040 electricity pathways for Southern Africa
- 3 • Wind and solar are likely to be the dominant forms of generation ca-
4 pacity by 2040
- 5 • No new coal capacity is required except when transmission is con-
6 strained
- 7 • Less than half of planned hydropower projects are economical
- 8 • An 80% clean energy target halves reference emissions at 6% higher
9 costs

10 **Context and scale**

11 Electricity demand is projected to double in the twelve countries of con-
12 terminous Southern Africa. The challenge is to meet this growing demand
13 while limiting carbon emissions and the socio-environmental impacts of elec-
14 tricity infrastructure. We developed optimal energy pathways for the region's
15 electricity sector. If current technology and fuel cost trends continue, wind
16 and solar dominate new capacity investments by 2040. No new coal power

17 plants are built, except when inter-regional transmission capacity is limited.
18 Despite abundant hydropower potential, less than half of planned project
19 capacity is economical, and the alternatives to hydropower appear to be a
20 viable pathway to avoid the socio-environmental impacts of large hydropower
21 projects. Electricity trade increases 15-30 times across scenarios, highlight-
22 ing the importance of further developing the inter-regional electricity market.
23 Lastly, meeting demand with 80% clean energy can halve emissions in 2040
24 compared to the reference scenario but cost only 6% more, an increase that
25 may be subsidized by international donors.

26 **1. Introduction**

27 The energy transition in Southern Africa epitomizes the twin challenges
28 facing developing regions: providing affordable energy services to meet grow-
29 ing demand while limiting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and socio- envi-
30 ronmental impacts. This region, encompassing twelve conterminous member
31 countries of the Southern African Power Pool (SAPP), is expecting a 60%
32 growth in population and more than doubling in electricity demand by 2040
33 [1].

34 With large coal resources in South Africa (14th largest GHG emitter
35 in the world and the largest in Africa), Mozambique, and Botswana, this
36 growth in energy demand could be met by new coal capacity, thus increasing
37 the region's GHG emissions. The large hydropower potential remaining in
38 the region's Congo and Zambezi rivers, two of Africa's five largest rivers,
39 could also be exploited, but at high environmental and social costs [2, 3]. At
40 the same time, new natural gas discoveries in the region and vast amounts of
41 high-quality renewable wind and solar resources may have the potential to
42 create a cleaner and cost-effective future electricity system [4, 5]. Although
43 Southern Africa, like other developing regions, has little historic responsi-
44 bility for anthropogenic climate change, their energy development pathways
45 will have profound implications for future GHG emissions, natural resource
46 conservation, and the livelihoods of local communities. Energy planning
47 in Southern Africa has largely relied on fossil fuels and hydropower, with
48 minimal roles for wind and solar technologies despite their rapidly declining
49 capital costs [1].

50 Previous studies of Southern Africa's electricity system have shown that
51 alternative, more sustainable energy futures may be possible. However, these
52 studies were carried out with analytical tools that only partially address the

53 many complexities associated with designing large-scale power grids. For ex-
54 ample, Wu et al. (2017) [5] estimated the regional availability of wind and
55 solar resources and assessed the high-level impact of transmission intercon-
56 nections on wind and demand variability, but without explicitly modeling
57 the transmission investments and operations of the region’s power system.
58 Other studies have examined power sector investments and electricity trade
59 in Southern Africa, but these either used models with low temporal and spa-
60 tial resolution that do not adequately capture the variability of wind, solar,
61 and hydropower [6, 7, 8, 9, 10] or did not optimize new transmission and/or
62 hydropower project investments [6, 7].

63 Moreover, none of the aforementioned studies explicitly represented hy-
64 dropower generation with spatio-temporal specificity using basin-level hy-
65 drologic modeling and project-specific energy availability. Representing hy-
66 dropower generation with sufficient spatio-temporal detail is critical given the
67 complementary roles that hydropower can serve in a high variable renewable
68 power system and the large potential and planned capacity that exists in the
69 region. Previous studies and current policies have focused on developing this
70 hydropower potential, especially for exports through regional interconnec-
71 tions [1, 11, 12]. These studies, however, may have overlooked the opportu-
72 nities that lie in coordinating the expansion of solar, wind, and hydropower
73 resources. Most previous aforementioned studies have not explored the value
74 of recent cost declines in wind, solar PV, and battery storage cost projec-
75 tions, which could potentially underestimate their role in Southern Africa’s
76 electricity futures. Other studies that have addressed these gaps did so only
77 for South Africa [13, 14, 15]. However, given the potentially important role
78 of regional electricity trade in enabling more renewable energy development,
79 it is critical to model the interconnected region as a whole.

80 To address these gaps, we developed energy pathways for Southern Africa’s
81 electricity sector by comprehensively characterizing the cost and potential for
82 both renewable and conventional technologies and balancing system costs
83 with GHG emissions and socio-environmental externalities. To design these
84 pathways, we developed a numerical modelling framework that explicitly ac-
85 counts for the spatio-temporal variability of current and future generation,
86 storage, and transmission resources across the entire region.

87 The framework uniquely links three open-source models that represent
88 renewable resources with high spatio-temporal detail. First, we developed
89 a detailed electricity system model for the twelve conterminous countries
90 of the SAPP using high spatial and temporal resolution wind, solar, and

91 hydropower generation data (GridPath). The GridPath platform can co-
 92 optimize generation, storage, and transmission investments and their op-
 93 erations across multiple investment periods under different economic and
 94 technical constraints [15, 16]. Second, to characterize the supply of renew-
 95 able generation for GridPath, we developed a renewable energy resource
 96 assessment model (MapRE) [17, 5] that captures the spatial diversity and
 97 temporal variability of wind and solar resources. Third, we developed VIC-
 98 Res-Southern-Africa, a process-based hydrological-water management model
 99 simulating daily river discharge and hydropower production across all exist-
 100 ing and planned hydropower plants [18]. We designed seven scenarios that
 101 explore the effects of technology and fuel cost trajectories and energy policies
 102 out to 2040 (Table 1)

Table 1: Core scenarios and assumptions

Scenario Names	Renewable energy costs Declining: Renewable energy and battery capital costs decline as per NREL ATB 'low' forecasts [19] Static: Current costs for both renewables remain the same as in 2017 out to 2040 [1]	Fossil fuel prices Rising: Prices for coal and natural gas increase based on SAPP's plan [1] Static: Fossil fuel costs remain the same out to 2040	Transmission Optimized Tx: Transmission (Tx) investments and operations are co-optimized with generation and storage capacity investments and operations Existing Tx: no new tx capacity Planned Tx: new tx restricted to current plans based on the SAPP Plan [20, 21]	Coal retirement 65 years: normal coal lifetime 55 years and 45 years: earlier retirements	Clean energy target None: no clean energy target 80% by 2040: 80% clean energy (wind, solar, other renewables, hydropower, nuclear) by 2040, roughly halving the annual 2020 GHG emissions by 2040.
Reference	Declining	Rising	Optimized Tx	65 years	None
Static costs	Static	Static			
Existing Tx			Existing Tx		
Planned Tx			Planned Tx		
Coal ret. 55y				55 years	
Coal ret. 45y				45 years	
Clean 80%					80% by 2040

103 We developed seven core scenarios with varying combinations of capital
 104 costs of solar, wind, and battery, prices of fossil fuels, transmission (Tx) in-
 105 terconnections, retirement (ret.) ages of installed coal fleets, and a clean elec-
 106 tricity target by 2040 (Table 1). The Reference scenario includes the most
 107 favorable set of assumptions for minimizing cost (extrapolation of current

108 cost trends, optimized transmission build, longest coal power plant lifetime).
109 Each core scenario then examines the impact of varying a key assumption
110 (e.g., static costs) or adding an additional constraint (e.g., clean energy tar-
111 get). As additional sensitivities, we also examine the effects of precipitation
112 variability on hydropower generation, limitations on natural gas capacity, and
113 additional interactions between costs, transmission, and coal retirements. We
114 evaluate the results in terms of optimal investments in generation, storage,
115 and transmission infrastructure, as well as system costs and GHG emissions.

116 **2. Results**

117 *2.1. Wind, solar, and hydropower potential*

118 We quantified and characterized wind, solar PV, and hydropower re-
119 sources in the region. For wind and solar, we spatially identified suitable
120 candidate project sites by excluding low quality resources, protected areas,
121 and unsuitable land-use land-cover types (e.g., forest cover, urban areas), and
122 then quantified their installed capacity and energy generation potential (Fig.
123 1). We found that generation potential for both wind and solar PV exceeds
124 future electricity demand (2040) in all countries, except Eswatini, which has
125 lower land use and land cover suitability for large-scale solar despite relatively
126 high solar radiation [22].

127 The region has large existing and potential hydropower capacity, with
128 eight out of the twelve countries currently dependent on hydropower for more
129 than half of their electricity generation (Fig. 1). Simulations of the VIC-Res-
130 Southern-Africa hydrologic model show that the average hydropower gener-
131 ation potential exceeds future electricity demand (2040) in two countries—
132 DRC and Mozambique—and exceeds half of the future demand in five ad-
133 ditional countries—Angola, Lesotho, Namibia, Zambia, and Zimbabwe (Fig.
134 1).

135 *2.2. New capacity and generation*

136 **Coal capacity has historically been a key generation technology**
137 **for the region, but continued investments in this technology will**
138 **likely be uneconomic with optimal transmission expansion.** Re-
139 sults from the optimal, least-cost planning scenarios using the GridPath
140 model show that no new coal capacity is required in any of the twelve coun-
141 tries of SAPP over the next 20 years, except when transmission capacity
142 is constrained (Existing and Planned Tx scenarios) (Fig. 2A). In these

Figure 1: (A) Installed capacities (2017) and existing and planned interconnection lines, (B) Capacities of existing and planned hydropower dams, (C-D) Capacity factors of solar and wind projects, identified by MapRE analysis, (E) Average hydro-electricity availability from existing and planned dams, simulated by VIC-Res. Black segments represent the 2040 energy demands. Energy demand for South Africa and Tanzania is greater than the y-axis limit and is not shown in subfigure E, (F) Average solar and wind energy availability with 2040 energy demands.

Figure 2: (A) Existing (hatched bars) and new (solid bars) generation capacities and (B) energy generation across 2020-2040 for seven core scenarios with varying renewable energy and fossil fuel costs, transmission capacity (Tx), retirement age of coal fleets, and an 80% clean energy target. Additional results for effects of limitations on natural gas capacity, additional interactions between technology and fuel costs, and hydro-climatological variability are provided in Fig. S1 and S2. Country-wise new generation capacities for the core and sensitivity scenarios are shown in Fig. S3-S8.

143 transmission-constrained scenarios, new coal power plants are deployed in
144 South Africa, Malawi, and DRC because Malawi and DRC are not well con-
145 nected to the rest of the SAPP, even when considering planned transmission
146 (see Fig. S3). When transmission is constrained, new coal capacity is also
147 required in South Africa, but only when renewable energy and fossil fuel
148 costs remain static or when coal plants are retired 20 years early (45 year
149 lifetime), thus replacing part of the retired capacity (Fig. S4). When Grid-
150 Path is allowed to build as much new inter-regional transmission capacity as
151 needed to minimize system costs, new coal capacity is completely avoided,
152 even if technology costs do not change or existing coal plants are retired early.
153 This highlights the pivotal role of additional transmission capacity along key
154 corridors in the SAPP.

155 **If technology and fuel costs follow anticipated trends, wind and**
156 **solar technologies are likely to cost-competitively dominate future**
157 **electricity generation investments in Southern Africa, and thus be**
158 **the dominant source of electricity in the region by 2040.** In all
159 scenarios except Static Costs, wind and solar PV comprise the largest share
160 of new capacity, varying from 23% to 42% and 36% to 44%, respectively, or
161 59% to 86% together (Fig. 2). In the Reference scenario, new solar PV and
162 wind capacities of 66 GW and 40 GW, respectively, are deployed by 2040.
163 To meet this requirement, the region would need to build 5 GW of variable
164 renewable energy capacity every year until 2040, which is approximately
165 five times the annual average installation rate from 2016 to 2020 [23, 24].
166 Note that capacity requirements are lower in earlier years and increase in
167 later years—which may be enough time to develop the required human and
168 institutional capacity. Balancing the additional variability of generation from
169 new wind and solar capacity requires 7-12 GW of 4-6 hours of battery storage
170 capacity. Most of the battery storage capacity is in South Africa because of
171 its relatively inflexible coal generation fleet and its large capacity of wind
172 and solar PV. In contrast, less than 1 GW of battery storage is required in
173 the Static Costs scenario.

174 Commensurate with new capacity installations, shares of wind and solar
175 energy together comprise the largest shares of total energy generation in 2040
176 across all but the Static Costs scenario. In the Static Costs scenario, share
177 of wind and solar reaches only 12% and clean energy—which also includes
178 nuclear, hydropower, and other renewable energy sources—meets only 29% of
179 demand in 2040. However, in the Reference scenario, the cost-effective share
180 of wind and solar generation more than triples to 39% and clean energy

181 doubles to 58% in 2040 compared to the Static Costs scenario (Fig. 2).
182 Retiring coal plants at 45 years further increases the share of clean energy to
183 70%, while the clean energy target policy has the highest clean energy share
184 by meeting its explicit goal of 80%. Surprisingly, increasing inter-regional
185 transmission capacity, which allows the region as a whole to access more
186 lower-cost wind and natural gas resources in specific countries, does not have
187 a significant effect on total renewable energy or clean energy shares, since
188 there is a concomitant decline in solar and hydropower generation.

189 **Retiring coal plants early can cut the share of coal generation**
190 **by 75% in 2040.** Limiting coal plants to lifetimes of 55 years and 45
191 years requires retiring 19 GW (49% of 40 GW installed) and 35 GW (88%),
192 respectively, of existing coal capacity by 2040 compared to 9 GW (23%) if
193 plants are retired after 65 years (Fig. S9). Consequently, the share of coal
194 generation falls significantly by 2040 as coal plants retire early—18% for 55
195 years and 6% for 45 years, compared to 25% for 65 years.

196 Due to the region’s significant existing and newly discovered natural gas
197 reserves and greater flexibility of gas generators compared to coal power
198 plants, natural gas becomes the largest source of conventional generation by
199 2040. In the Reference scenario, 28 GW of gas generation capacity is required
200 by 2040. This is one-fifth of total new capacity and 18 times more than the
201 region’s existing gas installed capacity in 2020. While 13% of this capacity
202 is built in South Africa, the rest is built in Angola, Mozambique, Namibia,
203 and Tanzania. With more favorable costs for fossil fuels in the Static Costs
204 scenario, natural gas becomes even more cost-competitive and its capacity
205 almost doubles to 50 GW by 2040 compared to the Reference scenario.

206 *2.3. Hydropower investments and generation*

207 **Despite the abundant availability of hydropower for future de-**
208 **velopment (43 GW of planned capacity [1]), less than half of all**
209 **planned hydropower capacity is needed in all scenarios.** In the Ref-
210 erence scenario, only 14 GW or one-third of planned hydropower capacity is
211 required (Fig. 2). If renewable energy and fossil fuel costs remain the same
212 (Static costs scenario), hydropower capacity additions reduce to 9 GW or
213 21% of planned capacity, because fossil fuel plants outcompete the proposed
214 hydropower projects. Even when coal plants are retired early, only a limited
215 amount of new hydropower capacity is built. In the most favorable scenario
216 for hydropower (Clean 80%), 20 GW or 47% of planned capacity is built. On

217 the whole, at least 23 GW or just over half of planned hydropower capacity
218 is uneconomic across all scenarios.

219 Notably, most projects planned in the DRC's Congo River basin, which
220 has one of the highest levels of undeveloped hydropower potential in the
221 world, are not required in any of our scenarios, including the most hydropower-
222 favorable Clean 80% scenario (Fig. 3). These projects include the Inga
223 dams, which are the largest proposed dams in the Southern African region
224 [1]. Selection of hydropower projects is driven mainly by investment costs
225 and annual capacity factors, but access to inter-regional transmission and
226 favorable seasonal generation profiles also play a role. With increasing fossil
227 fuel costs, more favorable costs for wind and solar (Reference scenario), and
228 a higher clean energy target (Clean 80% scenario), more hydro projects are
229 built, primarily those with lower capital costs and higher capacity factors
230 (Fig. 3).

231 Contrary to prevailing assumptions among power system planners and
232 investors [1, 11], new transmission interconnections, either optimally built or
233 based on current plans, do not seem to allow or encourage more hydropower
234 development (Fig. 2). In the Reference scenario where new transmission is
235 built optimally, new hydropower capacity slightly decreases compared to the
236 scenario with existing transmission capacity (See Fig. S3), and is replaced
237 mainly by wind and natural gas capacity as explained next.

Figure 3: (A) Projected hydropower capacities built under different scenarios as a percentage of available planned capacities. Size of bubbles indicates planned capacities of projects aggregated by basin and country, ranging from 40 to 16,994 MW. (B) Relationship between capital costs and annual capacity factors of individual hydropower projects and their built status by scenarios. Size of bubbles indicates planned capacities of the individual projects, ranging from 30 to 7,942 MW.

238 *2.4. Transmission interconnections and electricity trade*

239 **Transmission investments beyond planned capacity are needed**
240 **to avoid new coal and expand development of low-cost wind and**
241 **natural gas capacity.** Across all scenarios that optimally build new trans-
242 mission, inter-regional transmission capacity (defined by capacity-length or
243 MW-km) increases by 40-130% (Fig. 4 and Table S1) compared to the ex-
244 isting transmission capacity in 2020. All scenarios with optimized transmis-
245 sion build 2-8 times more capacity along inter-regional corridors than in the
246 Planned Tx scenario. Most of the optimally deployed transmission capacity
247 is built after 2030, allowing sufficient lead time from present day. Import-
248 antly, more transmission capacity enables more wind capacity by providing
249 access to better quality but geographically dispersed wind resources across
250 the region, and provides greater access to natural gas resources in Angola,
251 Tanzania, Mozambique, and Namibia to meet demand in the rest of the re-
252 gion. As a result, it avoids reliance on coal, specifically in Malawi and DRC,
253 and some battery storage and large hydropower capacity.

254 Inter-regional electricity trade increases substantially in 2040 compared to
255 2020 across all scenarios, enabling the development of spatially heterogeneous
256 low-cost renewable energy and natural gas resources (Fig. 4). By 2040,
257 while electricity demand doubles, total electricity trade grows to four times
258 the 2020 trade volume (Figs. 4G and S11) in the Reference scenario with
259 optimal transmission and higher shares of renewables. Static Costs and early
260 coal retirement scenarios show even greater electricity trade—about eight
261 times the 2020 trade volume—mainly to enable greater natural gas generation
262 exports from Angola, Mozambique, Tanzania, and Namibia. Thus, a high
263 renewable energy system (Reference and Clean 80% scenarios) may require
264 less transmission capacity and lower volumes of electricity trade compared to
265 a regional system with a high natural gas generation capacity (Static costs
266 and early coal retirement scenarios) (Fig. 4G) because of the concentration
267 of natural gas resources in a few countries.

Figure 4: (A-F) New-built transmission capacity over 2020-2040, and country-wise generation mix for 2040 across six scenarios. 'Existing Tx' scenario does not consider new transmission, and thus, it is not shown. (G) Total electricity trade across SAPP over 2020-2040. New transmission capacity tabular results are provided in Tables S1 and S2.

268 *2.5. System costs and emissions*

269 **Energy policy and market assumptions can significantly reduce**
270 **GHG emissions with minor annual system costs increases, except**
271 **if coal power plants are retired at 45 years.** In the Reference scenario,
272 GHG emissions in 2040 return to 2020 levels (Fig. 5). The Static Costs
273 scenario is the upper bookend for GHG emissions—increasing nearly 50%
274 over 2020 levels—because favorable costs encourage more fossil fuel capacity
275 and generation. The Coal Ret 45y scenario has the lowest cumulative carbon
276 emissions by 2040, with Clean 80% having similar annual emissions by 2040.

277 Early coal retirements limit GHG emissions but also result in higher sys-
278 tem costs. Retiring coal plants 10 years earlier (55 year lifetime) results
279 in 17% lower emissions in 2040 and only 4% higher costs compared to the
280 Reference scenario. However, annual GHG emissions decrease by 48% when
281 assuming 45 years lifetimes, yet costs increase by 13%.

282 Additional and planned transmission capacity alone only modestly in-
283 creases system costs and reduces carbon emissions. This is because even
284 in the Existing Tx scenario, electricity trade in 2040 is significantly greater
285 than in 2020, thus capturing the benefits of utilizing existing transmission
286 capacities for sharing resources and reducing system costs.

287 Adopting a high clean energy target (80%) can halve annual GHG emis-
288 sions to levels comparable with a 45-year coal retirement policy in 2040,
289 albeit with greater cumulative emissions. This higher clean energy target
290 is cost-optimally met with an additional 14 GW (21% increase) of wind, 45
291 GW (110% increase) of solar, and 6 GW (46% increase) of hydropower ca-
292 pacity compared to the Reference scenario. Meeting the 80% clean energy
293 target would result in annual costs that are 6% greater or 3 USD per MWh
294 more than the reference scenario, resulting in an average carbon emission
295 mitigation cost of 18 USD/MWh in 2040 (Fig 5). This annual cost increase
296 in 2040 is less than half of that for the Coal Ret 45y scenario.

Figure 5: Annual system costs (operating and investment) and carbon emissions across 2020-2040 for the seven core scenarios. Capital costs of existing generation infrastructure are assumed to be the same and sunk across all scenarios. They are thus excluded from total systems costs. Costs depicted here all increase over time because fixed costs of existing infrastructure comprise a greater share of total costs in earlier years. This does not imply that average annual costs increase over time.

297 3. Discussion

298 3.1. *Wind and solar will dominate if costs remain favorable*

299 In the absence of ambitious decarbonization policies, how renewable en-
 300 ergy and fossil fuel costs change will be one of the most important determi-
 301 nants of the balance between wind, solar PV, and natural gas investments and
 302 generation. Continued reduction in wind, solar PV, and battery costs [19, 25]
 303 can cost-effectively enable Southern Africa’s electricity system to limit its
 304 emissions to 2020 levels. But if costs remain static, least-cost investments
 305 would be dominated by natural gas capacity, and the region would require
 306 significant international financing and decarbonization policies to mitigate
 307 GHG emissions. Yet, historical trends and most forecasts are depicting a
 308 future with declining renewable energy and battery storage costs [26, 27] and
 309 increasing fossil fuel costs [1], thereby making a high renewable energy future
 310 much more plausible than one dominated by natural gas.

311 In this regard, our results are significantly different from those of previous
 312 studies, specifically the Southern African Power Pool Plan [1], which projects
 313 an electricity system dominated by coal, large hydropower, and natural gas,
 314 with wind and solar energy limited to only 2 GW, a small fraction of pro-

315 jected total capacity in 2040. Our results showing high shares of renewable
316 energy are similar to those reported by recent studies that assume the latest
317 technology cost projections but are focused only on the country of South
318 Africa [13]. We find a more balanced share of new wind and solar capac-
319 ity compared to more solar-dominated portfolios reported in other studies
320 [10, 28].

321 *3.2. Additional transmission capacity is needed to avoid new coal*
322 *capacity, but early coal retirements or clean energy targets*
323 *are needed to avoid coal generation*

324 Irrespective of cost trajectories, no new coal capacity is needed across
325 any of the scenarios, except when new transmission is limited to current
326 plans. This result reflects not only the large, high quality renewable resources
327 available in the region but also the availability of cost-effective domestic
328 natural gas resources. Yet, the share of coal generation in 2040 remains fairly
329 high (25% in the Reference scenario and 16% in the Clean 80% scenario),
330 unless coal plants are retired early. Early retirement results in low shares of
331 coal generation and thus in reductions of carbon emissions as well as improved
332 air quality and health outcomes—which have economic benefits that we did
333 not quantify in this study [29]. However, early coal retirement have higher
334 system costs because of the need to build replacement generation capacity.

335 In deciding whether and how early to retire coal capacity, policymakers
336 and stakeholders must balance potential emissions savings with potential in-
337 creases in system costs. International climate funding could not only provide
338 the additional direct costs of retiring coal early but also finance the em-
339 ployment opportunities needed to ensure an equitable transition away from
340 coal-based local economies [30]. For example, the US, UK, and EU recently
341 committed to USD 8.5 billion to support the phaseout of coal in South Africa,
342 the country with the most coal capacity and GHG emissions in Africa. As a
343 comparison, we found that achieving 80% reduction in emissions from South-
344 ern Africa’s electricity sector by 2040 will cost 9 billion USD more than the
345 reference scenario, while the cost to retire coal power plants at 45 years will
346 cost 17 billion USD more (Fig. S12). Note that these costs do not account
347 for co-benefits or impacts including those from improved health outcomes,
348 labor transitions, or GHG emission reductions. While the pledge to provide
349 support for South Africa’s energy transition is a commendable start, inter-
350 national financial commitments would benefit from being grounded in goals

351 supported by analyses to understand how much support may be required to
352 achieve a specific goal.

353 *3.3. Most planned hydropower is uneconomic*

354 Hydropower has remained a cornerstone of electricity planning in the
355 Southern African region largely due to the comprehensively-studied and in-
356 ventoried hydropower potential in the region. However, large hydropower
357 projects incur high upfront costs [31], often suffer from cost and time overruns
358 [32, 33], have substantial environmental and social impacts [34, 35, 36, 37, 38],
359 and are vulnerable to the impacts of climate extremes (e.g., droughts) [7, 39].
360 Results show that less than half of planned hydropower projects are se-
361 lected irrespective of policy or cost assumptions, including an 80% clean,
362 non-carbon target. Accounting for the risks of cost overruns and social and
363 local environmental impacts would only further diminish the number of eco-
364 nomic planned hydropower projects. We find that wind, solar PV, and bat-
365 tery storage are cost-effective and reliable alternatives to large hydropower,
366 which is similar to findings in other developing regions, such as Southeast
367 Asia and South America [40, 41, 42].

368 *3.4. Significantly increasing electricity trade will be necessary for* 369 *cost-optimal power system operations.*

370 Inter-regional electricity trade has declined in Southern Africa over the
371 last decade [43]. However, if the Southern African electricity system were
372 to operate cost-optimally, total electricity trade would need to increase by
373 15 times the current trade volume with Reference scenario assumptions, and
374 30 times with Static Costs scenario assumptions. Increasing electricity trade
375 will require SAPP member countries to address generation supply and trans-
376 mission constraints, make bilateral trades more flexible, and increase com-
377 petitive market trading [44, 43]. However, increased market-based regional
378 investments and dispatch may reduce national electricity sovereignty for some
379 countries by relying on imports and will require institutional strength and
380 political stability in the region to enable unhindered trade [28].

381 Increased transmission capacity in the absence of a clean energy target
382 can enable cost and emissions savings but these savings are modest. How-
383 ever, our simplified transmission model may overestimate the limits of inter-
384 regional electricity transfers by not capturing some technical and economic
385 constraints other than fixed transmission losses. If existing inter-regional

386 transfer capacities and flow limits are lower than our model assumptions,
387 then additional transmission capacity will result in greater benefits.

388 In summary, the Southern African region has tangible opportunities for
389 limiting future emissions from its electricity sector while also reducing elec-
390 tricity system costs. The key enabling factors are wind, solar PV, and battery
391 storage technologies that continue to decline in cost. Importantly, all energy
392 pathways only weakly rely on hydropower and most avoid new coal, thereby
393 limiting GHG emissions, improving health impacts, and contributing to pro-
394 tect ecosystems of key global importance. Enabling these pathways would
395 require decision-makers to critically reevaluate current power system plans
396 that rely on new coal capacity and uneconomic planned hydropower projects.
397 A transparent analytical planning approach with adequate representation of
398 wind and solar potential and costs, as demonstrated in this study, would be
399 critical in such a reevaluation.

400 4. Methods

401 4.1. Wind and solar resources

402 We adapted and built upon the Multi-criteria Analysis for Planning Re-
403 newable Energy (MapRE) modeling framework, which was first developed
404 for and applied to regions in Africa [5]. MapRE is a spatial energy systems
405 modeling framework that integrates renewable resource assessment and es-
406 timation of multiple criteria for decision making analysis [5]. Using wind
407 and solar average resource data sets [45, 46], and applying constraints on
408 elevation and slope [47, 48], and global and country-specific protected areas
409 and land use land cover data sets (Table S3), we spatially identified suitable
410 wind and solar PV sites across the twelve Southern African countries. We
411 conducted the site-suitability analysis at a spatial resolution of 500 m, and
412 then aggregated sites to 25 km and 100 km resolution for wind and solar PV,
413 respectively. The higher spatial resolution for wind sites reflects the greater
414 spatial variability in wind resources compared to solar.

415 Next, we developed hourly capacity factor time series for both wind and
416 solar PV using historical weather data. We used the same year—2018—for
417 creating the wind and solar generation profiles as the base electricity demand
418 profile. For wind, we used hourly wind speed data from ERA5 (European
419 Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts - ECMWF - Reanalysis 5) [49].
420 We adjusted the coarser spatial resolution ERA5 data for each candidate site
421 to match their annual averages to the average wind speeds at the nearest
422 locations in the finer spatial resolution Global Wind Atlas (GWA) data [45].
423 Average wind speeds in the GWA data are derived from a higher temporal
424 and spatial resolution data and are more accurate than ERA5, but GWA
425 time series data is not publicly available. We then applied a Vestas 2 MW 90
426 m turbine power curve to the modified hourly wind speeds to derive hourly
427 capacity factors using the System Advisor Model [50]. For solar PV, we
428 used hourly global horizontal irradiance (GHI) data from the National Solar
429 Radiation Database (NSRDB) derived from the Meteosat satellite [51]. We
430 again used the System Advisor model [50] to convert GHI data to capacity
431 factors for fixed tilt systems, setting the tilt equal to the latitude of each
432 location.

433 To estimate levelized cost components of extending transmission inter-
434 connections and roads to new wind and solar projects, we first estimated
435 distances of candidate projects to the nearest transmission and road infras-
436 tructure and then applied capital costs for 230 kV High Voltage Alternating

437 Current (HVAC) transmission lines [52] and asphalt roads to those intercon-
438 nections.

439 4.2. Hydropower simulation

440 To generate energy availability data for each existing and planned hy-
441 dropower project, we used a spatially-distributed hydrologic-water manage-
442 ment model. Specifically, we established independent modelling instances
443 for eight basins—i.e., Zambezi, Congo, Kwanza, Cunene, Rufiji, Orange,
444 Limpopo, and Buzi—which encompass more than 90% of SAPP’s total in-
445 stalled (~ 13 GW) and projected (~ 59 GW) hydropower capacity (Figure
446 1B). For each basin, we first used the Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC)
447 model (a large-scale, semi-distributed hydrological model; [53]) to simulate
448 daily runoff, evaporation, and baseflow with a spatial resolution of 0.0625° (~ 7
449 $\text{km} \times 7 \text{ km}$). The gridded runoff simulated by VIC is then routed through
450 the river network by VIC-Res, a water management model that simulates
451 daily river discharge as well as the storage and release dynamics of each
452 reservoir [18]. In VIC-Res, each dam is represented by a cell, whereas mul-
453 tiple upstream cells represent the water body. The water release through
454 turbines and spillway is determined by dam-specific rule curves accounting
455 for the reservoir water level, inflow, storage capacity, and downstream wa-
456 ter requirements (for irrigation and other purposes). The information on
457 hydraulic head (H_t , calculated from storage) and release through turbines
458 (R_t) is used with the gravitational acceleration (g), water density (ρ), and a
459 non-dimensional turbine efficiency term (η) in equation (1) to calculate the
460 daily (time, t) hydropower energy availability ($hydropower_t$) as:

$$hydropower_t = \eta \times \rho \times g \times R_t \times H_t. \quad (1)$$

461 Key inputs to VIC include a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and data
462 on soil, land use, land cover, precipitation, and temperature. The DEM and
463 data on soil, land use, and land cover are adopted from [54], who used the
464 30-m DEM produced by the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM)
465 [47], the FAO Harmonized World Soil Database [55], and the USGS Global
466 Land Cover Characterization (GLCC) dataset [56, 57]. For precipitation
467 and temperature, we used daily-gridded data from CHIRPS [58] and NOAA
468 Climate Prediction Center [59], respectively. To setup VIC-Res, we used the
469 global flow direction map [60] with the same spatial resolution of VIC. The

470 design specifications of existing and planned reservoirs are retrieved from
471 global reservoir and dam databases [61, 62], and complemented by basin-
472 specific studies on Zambezi [63], Congo [64], Cunene [65], Kwanza [66], Rufiji
473 [67], and Orange [68].

474 We simulated daily streamflow and daily hydropower budget for the 1997–
475 2016 period. Simulated streamflow at major dam locations closely match
476 with the streamflow data presented in [69] (Fig. S13 A-B). Additionally,
477 the annual and monthly average capacity factors of the dams are also vali-
478 dated against the capacity factors reported in [1] and [63] (Fig. S13 C-D).
479 These validations ensure that the simulation of hydropower budget captures
480 the hydro-climatic variability and operational constraints of the hydropower
481 projects.

482 *4.3. Electricity model and data*

483 To identify cost-optimal electricity infrastructure investments in the SAPP,
484 we used GridPath, an open-source power system modeling platform [15, 16].
485 Utilizing temporal and spatially-explicit demand, wind, solar, and hydro re-
486 source data along with various economic and technical constraints, Grid-
487 Path’s capacity-expansion functionality identifies cost-effective deployment
488 of conventional and renewable generators, storage, and transmission lines by
489 co-optimizing power system operations and infrastructure investments.

490 For this study, we developed the GridPath-SAPP model with 12 load
491 zones, each representing a SAPP member country. These load zones are
492 joined by transmission corridors that have existing, planned, and candidate
493 transmission capacities. We modeled five investment periods—2020, 2025,
494 2030, 2035, and 2040—each representing 5 years. The model can build new
495 infrastructure or retire existing infrastructure during an investment period.
496 Each investment period has a discount factor—7% for this study—that is
497 used to calculate net present value of costs incurred during that period.
498 Within each investment period, grid infrastructure is dispatched to meet
499 load and other constraints over 24 hours during 12 days, each representing a
500 month, and weighted appropriately to represent a full year. Energy demand
501 and supply is balanced in each modeled hour for each load zone. Hydropower
502 and battery storage energy availability is constrained over each day.

503 The model co-optimizes investments (over each 5-year period) in new
504 system infrastructure including generation, storage, and transmission, and
505 hourly operating costs, while meeting country-wise hourly electricity de-
506 mand, technical constraints on generators, storage, and transmission lines,

507 and other policy constraints (e.g., clean energy targets). New generation
508 capacities are selected linearly except for hydropower projects, which are
509 discretely selected (binary decision). Thus, the model solves a mixed-integer
510 linear programming problem. GridPath is written in Python and uses the
511 Pyomo optimization language [70]. The Gurobi solver [71] was used for all
512 simulations.

513 Key inputs to GridPath include projected hourly electricity demand for
514 each investment period, installed and candidate generation capacities, hourly
515 capacity factors of wind and solar generators, monthly energy availability of
516 hydropower projects, and existing capacities and unit investment costs of
517 transmission infrastructure. Other techno-economic parameters of the gen-
518 erators include fixed operating and maintenance (O&M) costs, variable O&M
519 costs, heat rates, fuel costs, start-up costs, ramp rates, minimum operating
520 levels, minimum up and down times, capital costs, plant lifetimes, emission
521 per unit generation, storage charging and discharging efficiencies, and trans-
522 mission losses. Major outputs are new-built capacities of generation, storage,
523 and transmission, hourly electricity dispatch, curtailment, and transmission
524 losses, exports and imports among the countries, operating and investment
525 costs, and CO₂ emissions.

526 For electricity demand, we created hourly time series for each investment
527 period based on actual 2018 data collected from the national utilities of SAPP
528 member countries. For DRC and Botswana, because of lack of access to data,
529 we assumed normalized demand profiles to be the same as Angola and South
530 Africa, respectively. For each month, we first selected a representative day
531 whose daily energy demand matched best with the average daily demand
532 for that month. We then adjusted each country’s hourly demand data to
533 South African Standard Time and linearly extrapolated the demand across
534 the investment periods based on annual growth rates and demand forecasts
535 (Fig. S14) reported in [1]. Projected electricity demand profiles are shown
536 in Fig. S15.

537 Existing generation capacities—mostly comprising of hydropower, coal,
538 and natural gas, with small shares of nuclear, oil, diesel, biomass, wind and
539 solar PV (Fig. 1A)—are adopted from [1]. Installed coal plants are assumed
540 to retire at an age of 65 years as default according to the maximum economic
541 lifetime of thermal plants [72], unless retired earlier in scenarios with shorter
542 retirement ages (55 y. and 45 y.). Power plants are not retired endoge-
543 nously. For new candidate generators, we considered coal projects in South
544 Africa, Tanzania, Malawi, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, Botswana, and

545 DRC, and natural gas projects in Tanzania, Mozambique, Angola, Namibia,
546 South Africa and Zimbabwe, based on existing capacities in those countries
547 [1]. We considered subcritical, supercritical, and integrated gasification com-
548 bined cycle (IGCC) technologies for coal and open cycle gas turbine (OCGT),
549 combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT), and internal combustion engine (ICE)
550 technologies for natural gas generators. New coal and gas generators are
551 assumed to utilize domestic fuels, except for the South African gas gen-
552 erators, which would operate on both domestic resources and higher-cost,
553 imported liquefied natural gas (LNG). Candidate battery storage, oil, and
554 diesel projects are considered for all countries. Small (<100 MW) biomass
555 projects are considered only for Malawi, South Africa, Eswatini, and Tanza-
556 nia [1]. Lastly, candidate wind and solar projects and their hourly capacity
557 factor inputs are simulated using MapRE, and candidate hydropower projects
558 adopted from [1] and their monthly energy availability inputs are determined
559 by VIC-res. Other techno-economic parameters of the generators are from
560 [1] and [73], while missing data are taken from global sources (Table S4).
561 Wind, solar, and battery storage costs are from [1] and their trajectories are
562 adopted from [19]. Coal and natural gas fuel cost projections are from [1]
563 (Table S6). Emission factors for fuels are from [74] (Table S7).

564 We assumed full coordination among the SAPP countries, with only
565 transmission losses and transfer capacities as constraints to electricity trade.
566 Existing and planned interconnection transfer capacities (Fig. 1A and Fig.
567 4A) are adopted from [21, 20]. Angola, Tanzania, and Malawi do not have
568 existing connections but have planned connections to the rest of the SAPP.
569 In scenarios other than the Existing Tx and Planned Tx scenarios, Grid-
570 Path optimally builds new transmission capacities along existing and planned
571 transmission corridors. Lengths of the interconnectors are estimated using
572 centroids of countries. Investment costs for new transmission lines and sub-
573 stations are from [75]. Annualized costs are scaled by ratios of thermal and
574 applicable transfer limits along each corridor based on [21] (Table S5). For
575 both existing and new lines, we assume bulk transmission losses of 1% per
576 100 miles [76].

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590 **Author contributions**

591 R.D., G.W., and K.N. conceptualized the study and acquired the funding.
592 R.D., K.C., G.W., and A.M. developed the methodology and software. K.C.,
593 R.D., and A.U. conducted the formal analysis. K.C., R.D., A.U., T.C., and
594 L.A. curated the data. R.D., K.C., G.W., A.M., S.G., and K.N. wrote and
595 edited the paper. R.D. and K.N. supervised the project.

596 **Declaration of Interest**

597 None

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890 **Supplemental Items**

Figure S1: (A) Existing and new generation capacities and (B) energy generation across 2020-2040 for the reference and sensitivity scenarios with varying renewable energy and fossil fuel costs and limited gas with coal retirement at 65 and 45 years.

Figure S2: (A) Existing and new generation capacities and (B) energy generation across 2020-2040 for the reference and sensitivity scenarios with wet and dry climate years. Wet and dry years are chosen from historical data from 1997-2016 (see Fig. S10).

Figure S3: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios with existing, planned, and optimized transmission interconnections.

Figure S4: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios of existing transmission interconnections with static costs or coal retirement age of 45 years, compared against the reference scenario with optimal transmission, declining RE costs, and coal retirement age of 65 years.

Figure S5: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios with varying renewable energy and fossil fuel costs and 80% clean energy.

Figure S6: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios with varying coal power plant retirement ages.

Figure S7: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios with 65 year and 45 year coal retirement ages and limited natural gas capacity.

Figure S8: Country-wise new capacity across 2020-2040 for scenarios with historical dry and wet years for hydropower.

Figure S9: Total usable capacity of South Africa's coal power plants over 2020-2040 planning period at different scenarios of retirement ages.

Figure S10: Anomalies of annual hydropower availability (TWh/y) at existing (upper panel) and planned (bottom panel) dams over 1997-2016. Red and blue rectangles indicate anomalies in the dry (2005) and wet (2008) years selected for sensitivity analysis.

Figure S11: Net export (-ve values) and import (+ve values) of electricity (TWh/y) by each country in 2020 and 2040.

Figure S12: Net present value of total costs (new generation, storage, and transmission capacity investments and operations) from 2020 to 2045.

Figure S13: (A) Correlation coefficients (R) between streamflow simulated by VIC-Res (this study) vs GloFAS [69] at major dams across eight modelled basins (indicated by the shades). (B) VIC-Res vs GloFAS streamflow for 1997-2016 period at two representative dams. (C) Comparison of annual capacity factors simulated by VIC-Res vs the factors reported in [1]. (D) Comparison of monthly capacity factors simulated by VIC-Res and WEAP [63] at two dams in the Zambezi.

Figure S14: Electricity demand growth rate (SAPP, 2017), and estimated peak load (MW) and annual energy demand (TWh/y) for 2020 and 2040.

Figure S15: Hourly demand profiles for each month, estimated from hourly electricity demand (MW) data (collected from utilities) of each country for the year 2018. Time scale in x-axis is in South African Standard Time.

Table S1: Total new transmission capacity built across six core scenarios (except Existing Tx scenario in which no new capacity is built).

scenario	total capacity (MW)	total length (km)	total capacity-length (MW-km)	ratio
Planned Tx	2300	3900		1
Static Costs	21100	9800		7.4
Reference	8300	7600		2.2
Coal Ret. 55y	13700	11000		3.9
Coal Ret. 45y	23600	12500		8
Clean 80%	9000	8300		2.8

Table S2: New transmission capacity (MW) built along inter-regional transmission corridors across six core scenarios (except Existing Tx scenario in which no new capacity is built).

transmission_line	Planned Tx	Static Costs	Reference	Coal Ret. 55y	Coal Ret. 45y	Clean 80%
Angola_Namibia	300	130	190	260	310	1010
DRC_Angola	600	2170	630	830	780	320
DRC_Zambia	0	0	440	370	420	900
Malawi_Mozambique	400	2860	2280	2310	2330	2140
Mozambique_Eswatini	0	4050	0	330	3340	0
Mozambique_Zimbabwe	0	1000	550	530	90	670
SouthAfrica_Botswana	0	170	0	0	100	0
SouthAfrica_Eswatini	0	3380	0	0	2780	0
SouthAfrica_Lesotho	0	3030	3020	5440	6080	2500
SouthAfrica_Mozambique	0	0	0	0	0	0
SouthAfrica_Namibia	0	2570	0	1630	4410	0
SouthAfrica_Zimbabwe	0	740	0	730	920	0
Tanzania_Zambia	1000	1000	970	1250	1500	1060
Zambia_Namibia	0	0	220	0	520	410
Zambia_Zimbabwe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zimbabwe_Botswana	0	0	0	0	0	30

891 **Supplemental experimental procedures**

892 *Wind and solar resource assessment*

Table S3: Description and sources of input data used in MapRE.

Category	Type	Data Source	Year
Boundaries	Vector	GADM V3.6, URL: https://gadm.org/download_country.html	2018
Elevation, Slope	Raster	SRTM CGIAR-CGI V4.1 by CGIAR Consortium for Spatial Information (CGIAR-CSI), URL: https://cgiasi.community/data/srtm-90m-digital-elevation-database-v4-1/	2008
Land Use Land Cover	GeoTIFF	Land Cover CCI Climate Research Data Package (CRDP) by European Space Agency - Climate Change Initiative (ESA-CCI), URL: http://maps.elie.ucl.ac.be/CCI/viewer/download.php	2015
Water Bodies	Shapefile	Global Lakes and Wetlands Database by World Wildlife Fund (WWF), URL: https://www.worldwildlife.org/pages/global-lakes-and-wetlands-database	2004
Rivers	Shapefile	Natural Earth V4.1.0, URL: https://github.com/nvkelso/natural-earth-vector/tree/v4.1.0	2018
Population Density	Raster	LandScan Datasets by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), URL: https://landscan.ornl.gov/landscan-datasets	2018
Protected areas	Shapefile	World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) by United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), URL: https://www.protectedplanet.net/en/thematic-areas/wdpa?tab=WDPA	2019
Roads	Shapefile	GRIP global roads database, URL: https://www.globio.info/download-grip-dataset	2010
Transmission	Shapefile	Africa - Electricity Transmission And Distribution Grid Map by World Bank, URL: https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0040465	2017
Wind	TIFF	World Bank Global Wind Atlas, URL: https://globalwindatlas.info/download/maps-country-and-region	2018
Solar	TIFF	World Bank Global Solar Atlas, URL: https://globalsolaratlas.info/download	2018

Table S4: Technical and economic parameters of generation technologies.

Technology	Capital cost ¹ (USD /kW)	O&M cost ² (USD /kW)	Fixed cost ² (USD /MW/yr)	Variable O&M cost ² (USD/MWh)	Heat rate (MMBtu /MWh)	Start-up cost (USD /MW)	Min. up time (hours)	Min. down time (hours)	Ramp rate (%MW/minute)	Lifetime (years)
Bioenergy	4263	142.8	142800	5.7	13.5	129	12	12	2	30
Coal (Subcritical)	2377	79.8	79800	6.9	9.3	129	24	12	2	30
Coal (Supercritical)	3739	79.8	79800	6.9	9.3	129	24	12	2	30
Coal (IGCC)	5779	122.7	122700	6.5	9.2	129	24	12	2	30
Gas (OCGT)	835	13.8	13800	4.8	10.9	79	0	0	8	30
Gas (CCGT)	1065	14.3	14300	5.2	7	79	10	8	5	30
Gas (ICE)	1140	12.9	12900	5.6	6.9	79	10	8	10	30
Diesel	1140	13.8	13800	5.6	11.48	69	0	0	10	30
Oil	1140	13.8	13800	5.6	11.48	69	1	1	10	30
Nuclear	6137	20		3.2	10.45					40
Geothermal	3500			10						30
Hydro	varying ⁴			4.5						60
Wind	varying ⁵	44	52300							25
Solar PV	varying ⁵	14	24400							25
Battery	varying ⁵	53.3	53300							15
Pumped-storage	3500	15.6	15600							50

¹ Capital costs are from [1].

² O&M costs, fixed costs, variable O&M costs, heat rates, and lifetime data are from [73].

³ Other data from different global sources including [72].

⁴ Project-specific capital costs of hydropower projects varies between 788-6,510 USD/kW with an average cost of 3,410 USD/kW, adopted from [1].

⁵ Capital costs of wind, solar PV, and battery varies over 2020-2040 as shown in Table S6.

Table S5: Economic parameters of transmission technologies.

Technology	Transmission capital cost (USD/MW-km)	Substation x 2 capital cost (USD/MW)
500 kV Double Circuit Line	960	22,470
230 kV Single Circuit Line	1,740	60,300

¹ Costs assumptions are from [52].

Table S6: Capital costs of wind, solar PV, and battery technologies, and fossil fuel prices.

		2017	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040
Capital costs¹							
Wind	(USD/kW)	1720	1600	1401	1201	1120	1038
Solar PV	(USD/kW)	990	804	654	503	431	377
Battery	(USD/kWh)	668	472	292	197	178	159
Fuel prices¹							
Coal	(USD/MMBtu)	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.1	3.2
Gas	(USD/MMBtu)	3	3.2	3.5	3.8	4	4.3
Gas (LNG)	(USD/MMBtu)	9.6	10.2	11.2	12.3	13.3	14.3
Oil	(USD/MMBtu)	8.5	9.6	11.5	13.3	15.2	17
Diesel	(USD/MMBtu)	11.3	12.8	15.2	17.6	20.1	22.5

¹ Wind, solar PV, and battery cost assumptions for 2017 are from [1]. Decline rates are from [19].

² Fossil fuel price assumptions for 2017 and escalation rates are from [1].

Table S7: Emission factors for fuels

Fuel	Emission factor (tCO ₂ /MMBtu)
Coal	0.106
Biomass	0.106
Natural gas	0.058
Oil	0.08
Diesel	0.08

¹ Costs assumptions are from [74].

Set	Index	Description
Π	π	Years or periods when investment decisions are made.
Δ	δ	Horizons over which storage/hydro is balanced.
$\Delta^\pi \subset \Delta$	δ^π	Horizons within an investment period π .
T	τ	Timepoints when operational decisions are made.
$T^\pi \subset T$	τ^π	Operational timepoints in investment period π .
$T^\delta \subset T$	τ^δ	Operational timepoints in a sampled day δ .
	π^τ	The year in which timepoint τ occurs.
	δ^τ	The sampled day during which timepoint τ occurs.
	hr^τ	Number of hours in timepoint τ .
Z	z	Load zones (or nodes).
ZF	zf	'From' load zones (or nodes) for transmission lines.
ZT	zt	'To' load zones (or nodes) for transmission lines.
BAR	bar	Balancing areas for regulation reserves.
BAS	bas	Balancing areas for spinning reserves.
RZ	rz	Renewable or clean energy target zones.
Γ	γ	All generator and storage projects.
$\Gamma^\epsilon \subset \Gamma$	γ^ϵ	Specified (including existing) generator and storage projects.
$\Gamma^\nu \subset \Gamma$	γ^ν	Candidate generator and storage projects.
$\Gamma^\mu \subset \Gamma$	γ^μ	Must-run generators (e.g. nuclear, biomass, biogas).
$\Gamma^\phi \subset \Gamma$	γ^ϕ	Dispatchable generators (e.g. CCGT, OCGT, Coal).
$\Gamma^\omega \subset \Gamma$	γ^ω	Variable generators (e.g. wind, solar).
$\Gamma^\sigma \subset \Gamma$	γ^σ	Storage projects (e.g. battery, pumped hydro).
$\Gamma^\chi \subset \Gamma$	γ^χ	Hydro projects.
$\Gamma^z \subset \Gamma$	γ^z	Projects associated with a load zone.
$\Gamma^{rz} \subset \Gamma$	γ^{rz}	Projects associated with a renewable/clean energy target zone.
Λ	λ	All transmission lines.
$\Lambda^\epsilon \subset \Lambda$	λ^ϵ	Specified (including existing) transmission lines.
$\Lambda^\nu \subset \Lambda$	λ^ν	Candidate transmission lines.

Variable	Description
$CB_{\gamma\nu,\pi} \geq 0$ $CE_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\nu\cap\Gamma\sigma,\pi} \geq 0$ $B_{\gamma\pi} \geq 0$ $E_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\sigma,\pi} \geq 0$	<p>Power capacity to install at each candidate project in each investment period.</p> <p>Energy capacity (i.e. power \times duration) to install at candidate storage project in each investment period.</p> <p>Power capacity at each project in each investment period.</p> <p>Energy capacity (i.e. power \times duration) to at each storage project in each investment period.</p>
$U_{\gamma\phi,\tau} \geq 0$ $O_{\gamma,\tau} \geq 0$ $C_{\gamma\sigma,\tau} \geq 0$ $D_{\gamma\sigma,\tau} \geq 0$ $F_{\gamma\sigma,\tau} \geq 0$ $CUR_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\omega\cap\Gamma\chi,\tau} \geq 0$	<p>Commitment level of each dispatchable generator in each timepoint.</p> <p>Power output from each generator in each timepoint.</p> <p>Charging of each storage project in each timepoint.</p> <p>Discharging from each storage project in each timepoint.</p> <p>Energy available in storage at the start of an timepoint.</p> <p>Output curtailment of each variable or hydro project in each timepoint.</p>
$Reg_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\phi\cap\Gamma\sigma\cap\Gamma\chi,\tau}^{up} \geq 0$ $Reg_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\phi\cap\Gamma\sigma\cap\Gamma\chi,\tau}^{down} \geq 0$ $Spin_{\gamma\subset\Gamma\phi\cap\Gamma\sigma\cap\Gamma\chi,\tau} \geq 0$	<p>Regulation up provision from each dispatchable, storage, or hydro project in each timepoint.</p> <p>Regulation down provision from dispatchable, storage, or hydro projects in each timepoint.</p> <p>Spinning reserve provision from each dispatchable, storage, or hydro project in each timepoint.</p>
$UE_{z,\tau} \geq 0$ $OE_{z,\tau} \geq 0$	<p>Unserved energy at each zone in each timepoint.</p> <p>Overgeneration energy at each zone in each timepoint.</p>
$CL_{\lambda\nu,\pi} \geq 0$ $T_max_cap_{\lambda,\tau}$ $T_min_cap_{\lambda,\tau}$ $O_{\lambda,\tau}$ $T_loss_{\lambda,zf,\tau} \geq 0$ $T_loss_{\lambda,zt,\tau} \geq 0$	<p>Transmission line capacity to install at each candidate transmission line in each investment period.</p> <p>Transmission maximum capacity in each timepoint.</p> <p>Transmission minimum capacity in each timepoint.</p> <p>Transmission flow on a transmission line in each timepoint.</p> <p>Transmission line loss at the originating (from) load zone in each timepoint.</p> <p>Transmission line loss at the destination (to) load zone in each timepoint.</p>

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Parameter	Description
$D_{z,\tau}$	Electricity demand or load at load zone in timepoint τ .
Π^f	First investment period.
$disc_factor$	Discount factor derived from the discount rate to calculate net present value.
$n_years_rep_\pi$	Number of years represented by each investment period.
tp_weight_τ	Weight of each timepoint based on number of timepoints or hours it represents in a year.
$B_max_{\gamma^\nu,\pi}$	Maximum cumulative power capacity installed at each candidate project in each investment period.
$E_max_{\gamma \subset \Gamma^\nu \cap \Gamma^\sigma, \pi}$	Maximum energy capacity (i.e. power \times duration) installed at candidate storage project in each investment period.
$SB_{\gamma^\epsilon,\pi}$	Specified power capacity (including existing) installed at each project in each investment period.
$SE_{\gamma \subset \Gamma^\epsilon \cap \Gamma^\sigma, \pi}$	Specified energy capacity (i.e. power \times duration) installed at storage project in each investment period.
$MSL_{\gamma^\phi,\tau}$	Minimum Stable Level of each dispatchable generator in each timepoint.
$Charging_Eff_{\gamma^\sigma}$	Charging efficiency of storage project.
$Discharging_Eff_{\gamma^\sigma}$	Discharging efficiency of storage project.
$CL_max_{\lambda^\nu,\pi}$	Maximum transmission capacity installed at each candidate transmission line in each investment period.
$SL_max_{\lambda^\epsilon,\pi}$	Specified transmission maximum capacity in each investment period.
$SL_min_{\lambda^\epsilon,\pi}$	Specified transmission minimum capacity in each investment period.
$T_loss_factor_\lambda$	Transmission loss factor for transmission line.

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Capacity Constraints

Candidate project capacity cannot exceed pre-defined limits.

$$\sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CB_{\gamma,\pi} \leq CB_{max_{\gamma,\pi}} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\nu}$$

$$\sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CE_{\gamma,\pi} \leq CE_{max_{\gamma,\pi}} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\sigma} \cap \Gamma^{\nu}$$

$$\sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CL_{\lambda,\pi} \leq CL_{max_{\lambda,\pi}} \quad \forall \lambda \in \Lambda^{\nu}$$

Total project power and energy capacity at each project is a sum of selected candidate projects and specified projects

$$B_{\gamma,\tau^{\pi}} = \begin{cases} SB_{\gamma,\pi} & \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\epsilon} \\ \sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CB_{\gamma,\pi} & \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\nu} \end{cases}$$

$$E_{\gamma^{\phi},\tau^{\pi}} = \begin{cases} SE_{\gamma,\pi} & \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\phi} \cap \Gamma^{\epsilon} \\ \sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CE_{\gamma,\pi} & \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^{\phi} \cap \Gamma^{\nu} \end{cases}$$

Transmission max capacity is either specified or is the new built capacity

$$T_{max_cap_{\lambda,\tau^{\pi}}} = \begin{cases} SL_{max_{\lambda,\pi}} & \forall \lambda \in \Lambda^{\epsilon} \\ \sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CL_{\lambda,\pi} & \forall \lambda \in \Lambda^{\nu} \end{cases}$$

Transmission min capacity is either specified or is the negative of the new built capacity

$$T_{min_cap_{\lambda,\tau^{\pi}}} = \begin{cases} SL_{min_{\lambda,\pi}} & \forall \lambda \in \Lambda^{\epsilon} \\ -\sum_{\pi=\pi^f}^{\pi} CL_{\lambda,\pi} & \forall \lambda \in \Lambda^{\nu} \end{cases}$$

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Generator Operational Constraints	
Dispatchable generator capacity commitment cannot exceed generator capacity.	$U_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} \leq B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\phi$
Power output plus upward reserves from dispatchable generators cannot exceed committed capacity.	$O_{\gamma,\tau} + Reg_{\gamma,\tau}^{up} + Spin_{\gamma,\tau} \leq U_{\gamma,\tau} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\phi$
Power output minus downward reserves from dispatchable generators must exceed or equal a minimum loading level.	$O_{\gamma,\tau} - Reg_{\gamma,\tau}^{down} \geq U_{\gamma,\tau} \times MSL_\gamma \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\phi$
903 Startup capacity at a timepoint is the difference between committed capacity in that timepoint and the committed capacity in the previous timepoint.	$startup_capacity_{\gamma,\tau} \geq U_{\gamma,\tau} - U_{\gamma,\tau-1} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\phi$
Power output of mustrun generator must equal their available capacity.	$O_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} = B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\mu$
Power output of variable generators cannot exceed their available capacity in a timepoint.	$O_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} = B_{\gamma,\pi} \times capacity_factor_{\gamma,\tau} - CUR_{\gamma,\tau} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\omega$
Net power output plus upward reserves from storage cannot exceed storage power capacity.	$D_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} - C_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} + Reg_{\gamma,\tau}^{up} + Spin_{\gamma,\tau} \leq B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$

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Net power output minus downward reserves from storage must exceed or equal the negative of storage power capacity.

$$D_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} - C_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} - Reg_{\gamma,\tau}^{down} \geq -B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$$

The energy available in storage cannot exceed the installed energy capacity.

$$F_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} \leq -E_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$$

Upward reserves from storage cannot exceed the energy available in storage in each timepoint.

$$Reg_{\gamma,\tau}^{up} + Spin_{\gamma,\tau} \leq F_{\gamma,\tau} - D_{\gamma,\tau} \div Discharging_Eff_\gamma + C_{\gamma,\tau} \times Charging_Eff_\gamma \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$$

Downward reserves from storage cannot exceed the available energy capacity in each timepoint.

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$$Reg_{\gamma,\tau^\pi}^{down} \leq E_{\gamma,\pi} - (F_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} - D_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} \div Discharging_Eff_\gamma + C_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} \times Charging_Eff_\gamma) \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$$

The energy available in storage must equal the energy available in the previous timepoint minus the net power output from the previous timepoint. Last timepoint of each horizon is defined as the previous timepoint for timepoint 1 of that horizon.

$$F_{\gamma,\tau} = F_{\gamma,\tau-1} - D_{\gamma,\tau-1} \div Discharging_Eff_\gamma + C_{\gamma,\tau-1} \times Charging_Eff_\gamma \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma$$

Power output plus upward reserves from hydro generators cannot exceed available capacity.

$$O_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} + Reg_{\gamma,\tau^\pi}^{up} + Spin_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} \leq maximum_power_fraction_{\gamma,\delta} \times B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^x$$

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Power output minus downward reserves from hydro generators must exceed or equal a pre-defined fraction of available capacity.

$$O_{\gamma,\tau^\pi} - Reg_{\gamma,\tau^\pi}^{down} \geq \text{minimum_power_fraction}_{\gamma,\delta} \times B_{\gamma,\pi} \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^x$$

907

Average power output from hydro projects plus curtailment during each horizon must equal the average fraction of available capacity during that horizon

$$\sum_{\tau \in T^\delta} ((O_{\gamma,\tau} + CUR_{\gamma,\tau}) \times hr^\tau) = \sum_{\tau \in T^\delta} (\text{average_power_fraction}_{\gamma,\delta} \times B_{\gamma,\pi} \times hr^\tau) \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma^x$$

908

Transmission Operational Constraints	
909	<p>Transmission flow cannot exceed transmission max capacity.</p> $O_{\lambda,\tau} \geq T_max_cap_{\lambda,\tau}$
	<p>Transmission flow cannot be less than transmission min capacity.</p> $O_{\lambda,\tau} \leq T_min_cap_{\lambda,\tau}$
	<p>Transmission loss for originating (from) load zone must be greater or equal to the negative of the transmission flow times loss factor.</p> $T_loss_{\lambda,zf,\tau} \geq -O_{\lambda,\tau} \times T_loss_factor_{\lambda}$
	<p>Transmission loss for destination (to) load zone must be greater or equal to the transmission flow times loss factor.</p> $T_loss_{\lambda,zt,\tau} \geq O_{\lambda,\tau} \times T_loss_factor_{\lambda}$
	<p>Transmission loss cannot exceed maximum transmission capacity.</p> $T_loss_{\lambda,zf,\tau} \leq T_max_cap_{\lambda,\tau} \times T_loss_factor_{\lambda}$ $T_loss_{\lambda,zt,\tau} \leq T_max_cap_{\lambda,\tau} \times T_loss_factor_{\lambda}$

910

System Constraints	
<i>Energy_Balance</i> _{z,τ} in zone <i>z</i> and in timepoint <i>τ</i>	
$\sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^\phi \cup \Gamma^\mu \cup \Gamma^\omega \cup \Gamma^x} O_{\gamma,z,\tau}$ $+ \sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^\sigma} (D_{\gamma^\sigma,z,\tau} - C_{\gamma^\sigma,z,\tau})$ $+ \sum_{\lambda,zf=z} (O_{\lambda,zf,\tau} + T_loss_{\lambda,zf,\tau})$ $+ \sum_{\lambda,zt=z} (O_{\lambda,zt,\tau} - T_loss_{\lambda,zt,\tau})$ $+ UE_{z,\tau} - OE_{z,\tau}$ $= D_{z,\tau}$	generator power output storage net power output transmission flow from zone transmission flow to zone unserved energy and overgeneration energy system load

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$Regulation_Up_Balance_{bar,\tau}$ $\sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^{\phi} \cup \Gamma^{\sigma} \cup \Gamma^{\chi}} Reg_{\gamma,bar,\tau}^{up}$ $\geq regulation_up_requirement_{bar,\tau}$	<p>regulation up provision from dispatchable generators, hydro, and storage in balancing area <i>bar</i></p>
$Regulation_Down_Balance_{bar,\tau}$ $\sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^{\phi} \cup \Gamma^{\sigma} \cup \Gamma^{\chi}} Reg_{\gamma,bar,\tau}^{down}$ $\geq regulation_down_requirement_{bar,\tau}$	<p>regulation down provision from dispatchable generators, hydro, and storage in balancing area <i>bar</i></p>
$Spinning_Reserves_Balance_{bas,\tau}$ $\sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^{\phi} \cup \Gamma^{\sigma} \cup \Gamma^{\chi}} Spin_{\gamma,bas,\tau}$ $\geq spinning_reserves_requirement_{bas,\tau}$	<p>spinning reserves provision from dispatchable generators, hydro, and storage in balancing area for spinning reserves in balancing area <i>bas</i></p>

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Policy Constraints	
$Clean_energy_target_{rz,\pi}$ in clean zone <i>rz</i> and period π	
$\sum_{\tau^{\pi}} O_{\gamma \in \Gamma^{rz},\tau^{\pi}} \geq clean_energy_target_{rz,\pi}$	<p>clean generator energy output has to meet clean energy target for that investment period</p>

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Objective Function	
Generation, storage, and transmission investment costs	
$\sum_{\gamma^\nu, \pi} \left(CB_{\gamma^\nu, \pi} \times annualized_investment_cost_p_mw_{\gamma^\nu, \pi} \right)$ $\times n_years_rep_\pi \times disc_factor_\pi$ $+ \sum_{\gamma^\nu \in \gamma^\sigma, \pi} \left(CE_{\gamma^\nu, \pi} \times annualized_investment_cost_p_mwh_{\gamma^\nu, \pi} \right)$ $\times n_years_rep_\pi \times disc_factor_\pi$ $+ \sum_{\lambda^\nu, \pi} \left(CL_{\lambda^\nu, \pi} \times annualized_investment_cost_p_mw_{\lambda^\nu, \pi} \right)$ $\times n_years_rep_\pi \times disc_factor_\pi$	<p>The cost of new investments in generation, storage, and transmission,</p> <p>levelized to annual payments and incurred in each investment period after a resource is built.</p> <p>No endogenous retirements are modeled here.</p>
Operational costs	
$\sum_{\gamma, \tau} \left(tp_weight_\tau \times hr^\tau \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \times disc_factor_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times O_{\gamma \in \Gamma\phi\cup\Gamma^\mu, \tau} \times var_om_{\gamma \in \Gamma\phi\cup\Gamma^\mu}$	<p>dispatchable and mustrun generator variable O&M cost</p>

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$+ \sum_{\gamma, \tau} \left(tp_weight_{\tau} \times hr^{\tau} \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \times disc_factor_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times \left(O_{\gamma \in \Gamma \times \cup \Gamma^{\omega}, \tau} + CUR_{\gamma \in \Gamma \times \cup \Gamma^{\omega}, \tau} \right) \times var_om_{\gamma \in \Gamma \times \cup \Gamma^{\omega}}$	curtailable (hydro and variable) generator variable O&M cost
$+ \sum_{\gamma^{\phi}, \tau^{\pi}} \left(tp_weight_{\tau} \times hr^{\tau} \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \times disc_factor_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times O_{\gamma^{\phi}, \tau} \times heat_rate_{\gamma^{\phi}} \times fuel_price_{\gamma^{\phi}, \pi\tau}$ $+ \sum_{\gamma \in \Gamma^{\mu} \cap \Gamma^{\nu}, \tau^{\pi}} \left(tp_weight_{\tau} \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times O_{\gamma^{\mu}, \tau} \times heat_rate_{\gamma^{\mu}} \times fuel_price_{\gamma^{\mu}, \pi\tau}$	dispatchable generator fuel cost candidate must-run generator fuel cost
$+ \sum_{\gamma^{\sigma}, \tau} \left(tp_weight_{\tau} \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \times disc_factor_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times D_{\gamma^{\sigma}, \tau} \times var_om_{\gamma^{\sigma}}$	Storage variable O&M cost (for batteries)
$+ \sum_{\gamma^{\phi}, \tau} \left(tp_weight_{\tau} \times n_years_rep_{\pi\tau} \times disc_factor_{\pi\tau} \right)$ $\times startup_capacity_{\gamma^{\phi}, \tau} \times startup_cost_per_unit_capacity_{\gamma^{\phi}}$	Startup costs for dispatchable generators
$+ \sum_{z, \tau} \left(tp_weight_{\tau}^{\delta} \times unserved_energy_penalty_z \right)$ $+ \sum_{z, \tau} \left(tp_weight_{\tau}^{\delta} \times overgeneration_penalty_z \right)$	Unservd energy penalties Overgeneration penalties

919